

The Constitution of Mollugogenol C. A New Sapogenin From *Mollugo Hirta*

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Recently we reported the constitutions of two new triterpenoid sapogenins, mollugogenol A (I)^{1,2} and mollugogenol B (IIa)³, isolated from *Mollugo hirta*. In the present paper we wish to describe the constitution of another new sapogenin, called mollugogenol C, isolated from the same source.

Mollugogenol C (IIb), C₃₀H₄₆O₂, m.p. 215–20° (dec.), $[\alpha]_D^{33} + 39.8^\circ$ (CHCl₃) gave pink → reddish violet colour in the Liebermann-Burchard test. It gave reddish-brown colour with tetranitromethane indicating the presence of a conjugated dienyl chromophore in mollugogenol C and this was further corroborated by the U.V. and I.R. spectral studies. The U.V. spectrum [λ_{max}^{EtOH} 243 (log ϵ 4.55), 252 (log ϵ 4.61) and 261 m μ (log ϵ 4.45)] of mollugogenol C was very similar to those of the 11 : 12, 13 : 18- dienes of the oleanane⁴ and ursane⁵ series and also to those of the 15 : 16, 17(21)-dienes of the hopane series³. The I.R. spectrum [ν_{max}^{Nujol} 788 and 771 cm⁻¹] of mollugogenol C was however compatible with those of the 15 : 16, 17(21) dienes of the hopane series (cf. mollugogenol B³). The I.R. spectrum of mollugogenol C also showed bands at 3500 cm⁻¹ for hydroxyl group and a strong band at 1702 cm⁻¹ which was attributed to a six-membered ring ketone. The keto group was a very hindered one as it was unreactive to any carbonyl reagent and could not be reduced by potassium borohydride at the room temp.

The nature of the carbon skeleton and positions of the oxygen functions in mollugogenol C were revealed by the transformations described below. Mollugogenol C on catalytic hydrogenation over Adams' catalyst in ethanol solution furnished dihydromollugogenol C (IIIb), C₃₀H₄₈O₂, m.p. 203–206°, which gave yellow colour with tetranitromethane. The I.R. spectrum of dihydromollugogenol C, unlike that of mollugogenol C, did not show any band at 771 and 788 cm⁻¹ but the band for carbonyl (1700 cm⁻¹) and hydroxyl (3440 cm⁻¹) groups were still present. Dihydromollugogenol C on oxidation with CrO₃-pyridine complex furnished a compound, C₃₀H₄₆O₂, m.p. 208–11°, which was found to be identical with the diketone (IIIc)³, m.p. 209–12°, obtained from dihydromollugogenol B (IIIa), by t.l.c., mixed m.p. and I.R. spectra comparison. Thus mollugogenol C could be either 3-hydroxy-6-keto-hop-15, 17(21)-diene or 3-keto-6-hydroxy-hop-15, 17(21)-diene. The latter structure was

1. P. Chakrabarti, *Jour Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 98.
2. P. Chakrabarti, *Tetrahedron* (in press).
3. P. Chakrabarti, P. K. Sanyal and A. K. Barua, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 96.
4. L. Ruzicka, G. Muller and H. Schellenberg, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1939, **22**, 767.
5. J. Simonsen and W. C. J. Ross, "The Terpenes", Cambridge University Press, 1957, p. 140.

however overruled because mollugogenol C, unlike the diketone (IIIc), did not respond to Zimmermanns' test for 3-keto group. Moreover the very hindered nature of the keto group in mollugogenol C could be explained only if the keto group is located at C-6 position. The diketone (IIIc) on potassium borohydride reduction gave dihydromollugogenol C (IIIb) in almost quantitative yield, thus showing the 3-hydroxyl group in dihydromollugogenol C as well as mollugogenol C to be β . On the basis of these findings, mollugogenol C may be represented as 3 β -hydroxy-6-keto-hop-15,17(21)-diene (IIb).

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